

FORWARD

(GA 824550)

Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

WP4 - Capacity building and training activities

REPORT

Deliverable 4.2 - Common training programme for OR's R&I actors

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INTRODUCTION

The D4.2 is the second step within the fourth Work package of the FORWARD project (GA 824550), “Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions”, as illustrated in the table 1. This deliverable goal is described in the GA as “A common training programme for ORs’ R&I actors will be developed to provide a common basis for the implementation of capacity building activities for R&I actors in the 9 regions.”

The D4.2 is focused on a “Common training programme for OR’s R&I actors”, dedicated to develop a “common basis” of capacity building activities, namely trainings and fellowships (advanced trainings), targeting R&I actors and aiming at improving competences in the Framework Program, European programs in general, and foster international outreach. This deliverable is very linked and embodies the general objective of the WP4, as stated in the GA: “the aim of this WP is to strengthen the collaboration between ORs and other research and innovation organizations in EU and Third countries, based on the results of the analysis carried out in WP2 and the thematic action plans of WP3”. Through the WP2 analyses and the initial works of the WP3 each OR had a common starting point to implement common actions linked to the WP4 goal.

The deliverable 4.2 (“Common training programme for OR’s R&I actors”) follows up the report of D4.1 (M18) on “Capacity building plan”, in which all the OR’s started the process of capacity strategy oriented by the WP4 methodology, presented by the WP4 leader. This process involved the analyzes of the data collected bottom up by WP2 and their conclusions, namely the joint strategy, as well as the initial process of organization of the Thematic Working Groups of the WP3. The conclusions from the work on these WP’s, especially on WP2, regarding the current state of the R&I communities, needs and strengths, as well as the defined FORWARD joint strategy, resulted into 9 Regional Capacity trainings. Despite the tailor made approach to each OR, and presented in Annex 2 of D4.1), the Deliverable 4.2 will focus on the common traits between these Regional Capacity Plan proposal, to be implemented in each of the 9 OR’s R&I ecosystem by the FW partners.

The Capacity Plan for FORWARD foresees a large range of activities, as stated in the GA goals (table 2). These activities are dedicated to build skills and capacity for improving the OR’s participation in FP, as: Trainings/workshops for researchers on EU Project Management and Project Development, for instance: “Project management and financial reporting of EC Projects”; “Writing H2020 successful proposals”; “Writing of the Impact Section”; “Management, coordination and implementation of coordinated projects”; “ERC: How to design a successful proposal”; “MSCA: How to design a successful proposal”; “Knowledge Transfer”; “Knowledge Protection”.

The D4.2 promotes actions that go beyond the target actions planned by FW project, promoting the engagement in other capacity actions with no cost for the project, as synergies, implemented at several levels, from regional to inter-regional partners, reinforcing cooperation

and collaboration between OR's R&I ecosystem. Also WP4 leader encourages to explore other interactions, namely for fellowships with Third countries and within R&I networks beyond EU partners, in case it's identified as a common interest, in order to promote international outreach.

The 4.2 is a common vision, of common traits of capacity actions, in a Capacity Building Plan that had its starting point as a tailored made approach, with 9 Regional Capacity Plans, directed to 9 different levels of maturity and experience regarding Framework Programs (FP). These differentiated approaches allowed the OR's R&I community more changes to successfully tackle opportunities of European financing for R&I projects, especially in Framework-programs.

Although this initial tailored approach, these plans have a shared matrix (methodology; goals; targets...), from which it was built, oriented toward a common goal. Therefore, it is possible to build synergies on common capacity needs/interests and analyze the Capacity landscape of the proposals, as a common capacities actions that represents the OR's Common Capacity Plan in FORWARD project. These common activity/goals/targets also allows the implementation of synergies between FW partners, reinforced by the digital tools that arisen and gained force in the present COVID situation.

Each region will implement these plans trough their consortium partner with competence in R&I policies and research.

In the context of the WP it's foreseen the following outcomes:

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D4.1	Capacity building plan	Report	Public	M18-M19
D4.2	Common training programme for OR's R&I actors	Report	Public	M18-M22*
D4.3	Common training programme for OR's R&I officers	Report	Public	M25
D4.4	OR R&I Offices Operational and Sustainability Strategic for implementation	Report	Public	M36

*Suffered delay due to COVID context

Table1 – Deliverables from the FORWARD WP4

Impact of COVID

The date of submission of the D4.1 suffered a delay of one month (M18 to M19) and the deliver 4.2 a delay of 4 months (M18 to M22) due to the impact of the Coronavirus pandemic. This international event affected the implementation of the WP4 actions locally and delayed the FW

team work on this regard in several partner institutions, namely in Universities, as a result of the worldwide public health restrictions, with online working, restrictions to travelling and implementing in-person initiatives, etc.

With the alteration of the initial previewed conditions, the digital means have given FW partners the opportunity to implement new and more synergies between regions and organizations, beyond the geographical constraints.

This situation has given more opportunities to create synergies between partners, however it also had a restrictive impact in with other type of synergies within the project at the level of WP's, like with WP5 (networking). Other formats of capacity initiatives, like Info Days, fellowships for trainings abroad and brokerage events had to suffer adjustments and demanded a great level of flexibility and restructuration of the program and tools to be put in to place by the FW partners, as well by the WP4 leader. The implementation of a digital solution is a need in order to tackle the limitations from the current world health situation that brought advantages and disadvantages, as well as great work towards a Capacity Plan that was possible to implement despite the Coronavirus situation.

In the context of the WP4 activities it was initially foreseen that the WP5 (networking) would have an important role in maximizing the outcomes in terms of engaging FP participation by opening opportunities for networking exchange activities and events participation at a regional, inter-regional, national, European and international level. This will continue to be the goal and the digital solution will allow that this will be partially implemented, in the digital context, although there will be a lack of informal networking from in person contact that the digital context does substitute.

Beyond the defined target

Along the WP4 implementation, as it was already refereed in the D4.1 report (important also in D4.2 context) and by the WP5 methodology, the partners are encouraged to use the possibility of cofounded capacity action, finding financing from other different sources. These sources may be Marie Skłodowska Curie action (MSCA_ITN; MSCA_RISE and MSCA_CoFund) or other regional funds to support their universities and research organizations. The digital context opens more options of synergies that should be explored and capitalized and it also reduces certain costs namely with the venue that financial barriers also gives the opportunity to involve more people on the WP4 activities. In Annex 3 there are 22 capacity actions that are not included in the FW budget and GA target activities. It's identified an effort ad commitment to the FW goals that goes beyond the defined target by the project.

The Forward partners are encouraged not to limit the WP4 activities to the budget attributed to the Regional partners by FORWARD project and plan other capacity activities that are aligned

with the WP4 goals, with no budget impact on FORWARD project. Several organizations and staff of the FORWARD partners are participating and being trained, through the assistance of the webinars and informative sessions organized by NCPs, or even by the European Commission and other Agencies (ORs Forum event; Water Europe Brokerage event; Green Week, Outermost Regions Forum ...). Those events are free and can add value to the overall goal of the project

On the other hand, in the case of ULPGC/FCPCT for example, in Canary Islands, the staff at the OPE (European Projects Office) have been participating in free webinars organized by EMDESK that cover topics such as CFS and audits, DMP, etc. Although these issues could be interesting for researchers too, these webinars can particularly be beneficial to regional officers (EU Project Managers). These webinars may not be listed in the regional Capacity Building Plan (CBP) presently but can be added on in a future revision of the CBP and for future indicators on WP4. The CBP is a flexible, ongoing tool in order to serve the best interest of the regions, going beyond the defined targets, when it comes to the GA and the FW budget, using every opportunity of capacity activities to empower their regional R&I ecosystem.

Joint Strategy impact

A joint strategy has shown a common starting point to the development of the Capacity Plan, even if the OR's are at a different level of maturity and capacity needs there is a common vision and goal expressed in the joint Strategy that impacts each Regional Capacity Plan (already presented in the D4.1 report). Therefore, the following joint action priorities are reflected in the 9 Regional Capacity Plan as a common orientation for WP4 Capacity Plans in FORWARD:

PRIORITY N°1: Design and implement more effective policies and funding schemes to increase the performance of the regional R&I system and FP participation

WP4 - Capacity building and training activities

- 1) To create opportunities for debate and peer learning: gather decision makers and R&I stakeholders, in order to learn more on EU and FP;

PRIORITY N°2: Create a collaborative strategy to Integrate major European networks and create critical masses

Two main subcategories: globalization; communication as a tool to promote excellence of OR's.

WP4 - Capacity building and training activities

- 1) Build a common OR training program for trainers and experts;
- 2) Training program for Researchers and SMEs on how to apply, how to communicate on their research.

PRIORITY N°3: Foster the FP-shift in R&I organizations

The focus is on performance, with three subcategories: (1), EU culture (2) and favorable environment for FP (3) and it has at his main target organizations and R&I system. This priority targets capacity building in research, EU culture and innovation skills.

WP4 - Capacity building and training activities

- 1) Promote innovation through training towards students in all OR universities;
- 2) Peer learning programs to support researchers to develop their entrepreneurial will and skills
- 3) A common OR training programme for trainers
- 4) Training on interpersonal skills, namely Leadership and team management
- 5) Training on entrepreneurship, coordination skills, project proposal writing

Even if we have initially 9 Regional Capacity Plans, adjusted to the maturity and size of each OR's R&I ecosystem, we can identify a common base of construction that reflects in each OR's the following common point identified as characteristics of a common FW Capacity Plan:

- 1) **Priorities:** Set by the Joint Strategy it defines the common priorities that has to be taken in to account and reflected in the common overall plan for the Capacity Building Plan in OR's R&I ecosystem;
- 2) **Synergies/networking:** Establishment of common opportunities of common capacity actions and trainings promoting the strengthen of the networks in the regional organization's and the opportunity to gather the actors from inter-regional to multi-regions;

- 3) **Common Target:** Even if each OR is at a different stage the identification of the target for their Capacity Plans are common in all OR's, independently of its size or experience with FP;
- 4) **Focus on the common final outcome** that is empowering the R&I ecosystem with skills and capacities to foster the participation of OR's organizations in European R&I programmes.

Image 1. Common characteristic that lead the 9 Regional Capacity Plans in to one common FORWARD Capacity Plan for the 9 OR's R&I ecosystems

TARGET & ACTIVITIES

This deliverable foresees the Capacity building and supporting activities targeted at the R&I actors from the quadruple helix (private sector, public institution's; researcher and universities and general public with interest in the FP) in order to promote or reinforce the project management skills to attain technical capacities in FP for themselves as well to pass on to support their teams and interested stakeholders in the region. As well as training administrative staff in EU project management: train trainer, as a sustainable perspective of the impact of these actions that should go beyond the duration of the FORWARD project.

In the common capacity actions included in every Regional Capacity Plan we identify the focus on the promotion of the R&I actors capacities to monitoring and identifying calls, identify project partners to built consortiums, submit, develop and manage FP projects, even if in different levels of approach. In this regard this thematic is further explored in common target areas in Table 2 of “Common target areas identified by the WP4 leader as a common FORWARD Capacity Plan”, further in this report.

The WP4 plan is to build a common Capacity Building Plan (CBP) that respects each OR's specific needs of the R&I actors in terms of skills and trainings, having in to mind the capacitation towards the present framework of the European R&I in the context of the H2020 - FP8, and future FP9, Horizon Europe and other financing Programs. The information mapped by each OR's and interpreted and diagnosed by the WP2 leader (NEXA) is essential to identify the transversal needs of the different quadruple helix that was the support to building the CBP.

The WP4 leaders received 9 Plan Proposals, taking into account the GA target actions previewed in the project budget attributed to Forward partner's within this WP. These Plans are available in Annex 2 (target activities) and Annex 3 of the D4.1 report (overall activities, beyond the project targets) of the WP4 documents (D4.1), submitted in M9 to the European Commission.

The target activities already proposed in D4.1 includes a **total of 78 fellowships to attend abroad and 61 training/capacity initiatives, as workshops, training, mutual learning activities.** These activities have as target the actors of the R&I in OR's and the dominant key words in the description of the target actors are as illustrated in Image 2, a word cloud for WP4 target actors.

Image 2. Keywords cloud sourced by the Annex 2 (D4.1), Target Actions of the WP4

WP4 Operationally

Reinforcing what was already mentioned in the context of the D4.1 report, the WP4, as a Capacity Building FORWARD Work Package, is engaged in following the new trends on online learning skills, having the present and future needs regarding the current constraints of the international health pandemic (had its peak in March 2020 and still ongoing).

Capacity buildings should resource digital methods as **e-Learning, web-seminars and podcasts**. The use of digital tools can also help to overcome our geographical constraints as Outermost Regions to a certain degree.

The platforms to be used to implement the actions should be from the responsibility of each FW partner, resourcing to already used digital platforms in their organization or if needed include any cost of utilization of these platform in the WP4 budget, keeping the costs within the previewed budget for these actions in the project budget.

Although the increasing importance in using digital tools, we should have in to account that the in-person meetings are still essential to engage and potentiate human interactions, adding value and potentiating the WP4 activities outcomes, as well as contributing for other WP synergies, as WP5 (networking). When possible the option of the in-person events (if possible, under the current legal restrictions and safety measures) should be privileged.

Fellowships

Researchers will be supported to attend either training organized locally in the framework of the project or other trainings of excellence organized abroad, as initially planned in the GA of the project. Although there is always a question mark regarding the present situation of COVID pandemic that is still restraining this part of the foreseen actions of the capacity plan, therefore it may suffer some adjustments. In order to assure its implementation there should be a focus

on the final goal and adjust the way to implement in the current context, namely turn the training abroad, that implies in-person trips, into digital participations. The important thing is to ensure that the goal is reached and that will be an exchange of advanced knowledge that leads to possible development of cooperation activities. The FW partners should follow up the advance of the current situation and adjust accordingly, being by this definition an ongoing planning. Any propositions to adjust the spirit of the fellowships from in person to digital option should inform the WP4 leader.

One of the main goals of these specific actions is to access excellence by contacting with realities that are involved at another level with FP programs and allow them to be closer to the centers of decision making in the European Union. These fellowships goals are international widening and capacitation that should be assured. Even if it is required to choose the online option, it should be clear the impact and skills gained through this digital activity in the implementation report (Annex 4 from D4.1)

The WP4 leader as well as the all consortium are aware of the uncertainty of the present COVID situation that is a challenge that was not taken in consideration when the proposal was written. Although the need to be flexible and adjust should allow the advance of this WP and the all project, with the focus on the goal and in its priorities. The fellowships, however the choice is - in person or digital participation - should implement activities as training, seminars, webinars, MOOCs/online courses, and/or summer school activities, and maintaining the original spirit of these activities as well as target the same beneficiaries.

Synergies

We can identify synergies in WP4 at several level, between WP's, or within the WP4, with activities that can be shared between FW partners, at a regional, inter-regional or multi-regional or other partnerships (evolving Third countries) that can bring added value to the FW in the implementation of capacity activities. These different levels of synergies empowers and promotes a more effective impact of the WP4 activities, as it reinforces collaboration and transversal results (networking; better understating of other realities and partners, etc) of the WP4 activities

The sharing of information and best practices on management of EU FP programs, as well as other international programs activities for FORWARD partners have already started with mutual learning events and in- person events, namely in Brussels with the FORWARD partners in 2019 (illustrated in Image 2). These activities have shown that it is fundamental to reinforce links between partners in order to support the rapid and efficient evolvement of OR partners and help the exchange of knowledge. Despite the COVID situation, the FORWARD partners are encouraged by the WP4 leader, and through the regional WP4 regional coordinators to open

space for synergies, since the situation of COVID can turn this challenge into an opportunity of breaking the barrier of geography and allow more and intensified synergies in WP4 activities.

Following an initial process of tailoring Capacity Plans, each regional partner is invited to re-analyze the OR's Capacity Plans as an all. By looking in to their own activities proposals and the other partners, in the several ORs, they may define points of common interest and potential synergies in the implementation of the capacity activities. The WP4, in coordination with the WP4 regional coordinators have launch that challenge to their regional partners: take as an advantage the digital events (due to COVID) and create common capacity activities. The annex 1 of this document presents the slides from a meeting with the WP4 Regional coordinators that marked the kick-off of this process, with the presentation of the regional proposal for synergies. A starting point that opens the door to more synergies and reinforced networking between the OR's and their R&I actors.

The WP4 intend to make the Capacity Building Plan an ongoing process were all the FW partners have the opportunity to analyze the option of joint events, finding common interest and promoting more activities, that can share the costs, exchange participation in trainings, or either share free opportunities.

This multi-regional synergies reinforces the ultimate goal of achieving the capacitation of the R&I actors and empower all OR's R&I ecosystem. Even if each has a different starting point they are all guided towards a common goal that the synergies empowers through mutual development.

In this context the Advisory Board (AB) members were challenged in the FORWARD AB meeting of 22th of October 2020 to build synergies with the FW partners. The WP4 leader launched this request to the AB members to offer training/experience online, exchange experiences with FORWARD partners, even to the R&I ecosystem, if they are available to do so. This can be a way to deepen their interaction with the project and engage them in a volunteer base with the WP4 goals and contribute to the goals of the project by sharing expertise, reinforce project managing knowledge on FP projects, networking and incentive exchange of ideas, advises and experiences.

IMPLEMENTATION

The Regional Capacity Plan are focused on the implementation of capacity actions fundamental to the OR's R&I ecosystems to increase the more efficient participation in FP (Horizon 2020 and the following program, Horizon Europe) and other EU R&I funding programmes.

The Capacity Building has as minimum of target capacity actions previewed in the GA of 78 Fellowships to attend training abroad and 61 Trainings. In total, the FORWARD partners have access to 139 financed capacity and training actions, as presented in table 2 of this chapter.

There are also 22 proposals of capacity action that are beyond the defined target by FORWARD GA attributed by partner. These actions will be supported financially outside the previewed budget for these actions in FORWARD, with no impact on the FW budget, from several sources, from free events from EC to internal financed trainings, to National Contact Points training. You can see in annex 2 of this document the presentation of graphics that represent the training activities per region and their thematic, with the overall activities, financed and non-financed actions of capacity building.

The deadline for submitting the deliverable 4.2 was delayed by 4 months due to the Coronavirus pandemic, since the actions implementation suffered an impact, especially regarding the activities of "mutual learning events and twinning actions", linked with WP5 (networking). With the changes imposed by the health world pandemic, most organizations had to adjust their activities to digital platform. This can be analyzed in two angles: a positive change that allowed the break of geographical barriers making every region and target actors accessible through digital platforms; on the other hand, it poses a problem to implement synergies between WP's, as for example the WP4-WP5 (networking). Since the digital solution lacks the informal networking, fundamental to build work/inter-personal relations and understand better the partners/stakeholders and their goals.

Analyzing per target group in the R&I ecosystem we can identify the following: there are available capacity action for researchers on specific training/workshop for proposals development; project management; transfer scientific excellence; innovation entrepreneurship. For companies, industry & cross-sectoral collaboration there is an offer of events and trainings; creation of spin-offs; public-private; partnerships, etc. For OR's officers teams it was designed capacity action that provide

technical support to advice and orient R&I actors in EU Framework Program. For Forward consortium there is an ongoing capacity actions that has already started, namely in the Mutual Learning event in Brussels, in October 2019 (picture 1, bellow), and other co-construction Workshops an attending international research events, as in Reunion Island in July 2019. Although that Corona situation already forced the partners to delay the initial meeting that was meant to happen during the research international event in French Guyana in October 2020, putting for now a question mark regarding the next opportunity to implement this action in the context of in-person activity between the project managers of FORWARD.

The decision makers are also target for capacitation actions, namely trough the engagement on events to create awareness on FP importance in order to enable the Strategic Roadmap for the implementation of the OR R&I Offices.

Image 2. Group works between FORWARD partners for exchange of knowledge, ideas and experiences regarding the project priorities and actions, Mutual Learning event in Brussels, October 2019

The Capacity Building plan will be implemented by each partner with competence in R&I policies and research in their respective OR's based on the analyses of needs that were analyzed in the WP2 diagnose and mapping and mentioned in the D4.1 report.

The training activities in the OR's R&I ecosystem the WP4 will follow the initial steps within the new calendar adjustments due to the world pandemic situation, as is it is illustrated in the below in Image 3.

Image 3, WP4 Roadmap adjusted to the impact from the world health pandemic (COVID). Source: WP4 leader

Methodology

The WP4 will follow up the implementation of the Regional Capacity Plans in the several OR's with the help and assistance of the WP4 Regional Coordinators (one representative per OR). These are the privileged regional contact in representation of its FW regional partners and are in close communication with the regional partners and their OR's R&I community, bridging them with the WP4 leader in FORWARD project. Their task are ,namely, to provide and manage the information regarding the activities taking place regionally and helping the WP4 with information for the WP4's reports, within the defined deadlines set by the WP4 leader. The WPL and the Regional Coordinators should maintain a bilateral/multilateral exchange of information by emails and during meetings, in order to update and managed an overall follow-up of the WP4. The following Table 1 shows the name and contacts of the nominated FORWARD WP4 Regional coordinator per OR.

FORWARD WP4 Regional Coordinators		
Regions	Name	Email
GUADALUPE	Sophie Larrieu	slarrieu@cr-guadeloupe.fr
MARTINIQUE	Philippe HUNEL	philippe.hunel@univ-antilles.fr
MADEIRA	Élia Vieira	elia.vieira@staff.uma.pt
REUNION	Evelyne Tarnus	evelyne.tarnus@nexa.re

MAIOTE	Hadel LAOU MADI)	hadel.laou-madi@cg976.fr
FRENCH GUIANA	Laurent LINGUET f	laurent.linguet@univ-guyane.fr
AZORES	Lina Silveira	lina.FM.silveira@azores.gov.pt
SAINT MARTIN	Junisa Gumbs	junisa.gumbs@com-saint-martin.fr
CANARY ISLANDS	Almudena Suarez; Noelia Díaz (suplent)	almudena.suarez@ulpgc.es; noelia.diaz@ulpgc.es

Table 1. Common target areas defined by WP4 leader in order to analyze the Regional capacity building in FW

The lead will be taken by FRCT, as WP4 leader, in order to maintain the needed frequent exchanges of emails and organization of technical meetings with WP4 Regional coordinators in order to keep track on the implementation process and any other actions, regarding synergies, any given difficulty or other issues that may arise regarding WP4 activities. On the other hand, the WP4 Regional Coordinator should also held frequent meetings and follow up the implementation process of the WP4 in its region by their FORWARD partners and report to WP4 leader within the requested/defined deadlines for tasks.

Content and references

The Regional Capacity Plans presents a list of trainings and capacity building initiatives per OR built up having in to consideration the following information:

1. The GA orientation regarding the target trainings to include in the Capacity Plan (table 2);
2. The result of WP2 diagnose regarding the inputs of the actors of the R&I ecosystem, it's needs in terms of capacities - combination of quantitative to qualitative info gathered directly from each R&I ecosystem;
3. Approval of the FW partners of the Capacities Plan and D4.1, taking in to account the information collected previously (WP2; WP4), as an initial process of adjustment of the Plan to each reality in the OR's;
4. The Annex 2 and Annex 3 from D4.1, as ongoing tables of work and follow up of the capacity actions implemented and to be implemented.

As examples of common trainings suggested in the GA for capacity actions we have: "Project management and financial reporting of EC Projects"; "Writing H2020 successful proposals"; "Writing of the Impact Section"; "Management, coordination and implementation of coordinated projects"; "ERC: How to design a successful proposal"; "MSCA: How to design a successful proposal". These targets were followed by each FORWARD partner in their presentation of Regional Capacity Building, taking in to account the targets defined by the GA per FW-partner organization and that we can consult in the following table 2. This table presents the number of capacity and training actions per OR in the FORWARD project as a target in FW GA:

	AZO	CAN	GUA	GUY	MAD	MAR	MAY	REU	SAI
Trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development	3	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1
Workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation	3	3	3	2	2	0	1	3	0
Trainings on scientific excellence in research	3	5	3	2	1	0	0	2	0
Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	2	2	2	2	1	0	0	1	1
Researchers attending trainings abroad	5	10	7	20	20	6	0	10	0
R&I actors participating in the capacity actions	20	62	60	5	20	3	2	30	2
Regional meetings for MoU's preparation	2	2	1	1	1	0	0	1	0

Table 2. WP4 implementation indicator, source: GA FORWARD

Following the WP2 diagnostic of the OR's R&I ecosystem the conclusion was that due to the different maturity and characteristics of the OR's R&I regional community there was a need to create a Capacity Plan that adjusted to the regional reality. These plans were created and presented in the D4.1 (annex 2) and previously completed with the Annex 3 (D4.1). The difference between Annex 2 and Annex 3 is that the Annex 3 include also other trainings that are not included in the GA target actions (pointed in annex 1 from D4.1 and in Table 1 of the current document). This was also an opportunity to allow each OR to adjust their capacity building plan to the current situation of COVID 19, changing the way it was going to be implemented and even providers and goals, adjusted to the digital, safer option, or adjust it into smaller training groups, as also to adjust the fellowships to advance training online.

In Annex 2 of this document it is possible to see the graphical analyzes of the 9 Capacity Building Plans, per OR, with the description of type of trainings, in detail. This exercise allows each OR to see the state of art of their Capacity Plan and their focus areas that analyzed as a common action plan in Graphic 1.

Common analyze of the Capacity actions

Extracting and analyzing the information of the Annex 3 (table from D4.1), provided by the FW-partners regarding their Capacity Building actions it was possible to analyze common traits and have a common view of the Capacity training landscape in the OR's R&I ecosystems. This table also included training activities that goes beyond the GA attributed budget, with 22 other training courses. The total of capacity activities in FW Capacity Building Plan accounts for an overall of 143 activities.

The WP4 leader created a tool that allowed to create a common base of analyses of the FW-OR's partners and was able to identify 3 areas that were in line with WP4 goals within the FORWARD overall goals for the OR's. The following table 3 of "Target Areas for Capacity Building" identifies 3 areas as the base for organization and analyses of these 9 regional proposals of CBP:

FORWARD - Target areas for capacity building		
Forward skills	EU Funding	Human Resources capacities
Management in Innovation	H2020 / Horizon Europe	Financial management
Project Manager	LIFE + and BEST	Training in specific areas – based on the WP3 areas
Identification of calls, successful proposals and managing founds	European funds regionally managed (FSE, FEDER, INTERREG B, etc.)	Development of soft skills (network building; team management; time; managing)
Communicating science	Call for Tenders - UE	Coaching in science
Stakeholders engagement strategy	Others EU funds managed by the EC (Maritime funds, INTERREG EUROPE, MAES, etc.)	Entrepreneurship
Knowledge transfer	Deep knowledge and alignment on EU networks, like ERA, RIS3 and Regional development	Writing impact sections

Table 3. Common target areas identified by the WP4 leader as a common FORWARD Capacity Plan

We identified the areas of choice by having as a starting point the main capacity skills to attain in order to have a more prepared and informed actors in the OR'S R&I ecosystems. Firstly the **FORWARD skills**, as the ground base for increasing the FP that are linked to FW actions and main target; the **EU funding area** is focused overall in awareness and knowledge actions on R&I founding and networks that can be accessed by the OR's R&I actors (FP; thematic calls and programs; EU networks, like ERA, RIS3 and Regional development, etc); the final area is **Human**

Resources capacities, as a transversal knowledge that allows the R&I actors to have skills that elevate the quality and capacity of the R&I actors, with focus on FP participation, as promoting a different conscience (entrepreneurship), concrete knowledge (financial skills), soft skills, English language and other transversal capacities.

Table 3 allowed us to identify the main areas that the WP4 is dedicated in terms of capacity building and it allowed the graphical representation that revealed the common CB landscape in the FW OR’s R&I ecosystem, as represented in graphic 1.

Graphic 1. Common Capacity Building Plan for the OR’s R&I actors in FW project

This graphic represents the 3 areas of capacity building that are the core capacity skills of the R&I ecosystem in OR’s that includes all the planned capacity actions in the OR’s, included the already implemented and the ones to be implemented, as well as the actions that are within and beyond the FW budget attributed to WP4 activities. This graphic represents the total work foreseen by the OR’s FW partners within this WP.

By analyzing the graphic of Common Capacity Actions in WP4 for R&I actors we conclude that the FW partners have focused primarily in the area of FORWARD skills (59 actions), accounting the larger number of activities under this area. These are the capacity skills focused on the active engagement in improving the capabilities in order to increase the participation of the OR’s R&I ecosystem on FP projects. The second area with the most capacity activities is the Human Resources (42) , more focused on the personal capacity, namely soft skills and other transversal skills, that can make a difference in terms of quality and human ability to attain the success on the application and management of this EU funded projects. In third place we present the area dedicated to EU funds (40), it includes networks knowledge, introductory/awareness actions on EU funds on R&I, FP, but not only, and capacity trainings on promotion and alignment with the EU networks.

OPERATIONAL WORK PLAN

The COVID situation jeopardized the initial plan and forced the change of some actions that were initially planned to be in person, namely fellowships for training abroad - that required travelling - are still on hold or the digital option has been taken. The digital platforms allow to keep the activities going on despite the constraints. Also the role of the WP4 Regional Coordination gained a larger importance creating a stronger link between the regional partners and bridge the regional updates with the WP4 leader. All WP's had the need to restructure their operational plan, as it was the case of the WP4 that previewed several in-person capacity and training activities. The FW partners are keeping a close watch on the development of the situation in 2020 as well in 2021 in order to adjust actions and define the way the fellowships will be implemented. Due to this situation, many FW partners have postponed the implementation of capacity actions to 2021.

Ongoing process of proximity

The Capacity Building Plan is an ongoing process, adjusting and finding ways to empower the impact of its actions, despite the current limitations and going beyond the defined targets in the FW GA. The situation of COVID required a capacity to deal with an unprecedented situation therefore, it required also from the FW partners a higher capacity to compromise, adjust e re-planning. In this context the role of the Regional Coordinator for WP4 is essential to keep a constant communication regarding the needed adjustments have been put in to place. Also there was also the identification of an opportunity within the COVID limitations, by turning the actions in to digital platform that allows the FW-partners to build multi-regional synergies, reinforcing their network and allowing more R&I actors to participate in more actions, by exchange of participation. These synergies have been increasingly promoted and encouraged by the WP4 leader and its Regional Coordinators.

In the Annex 1 of this document you can find the power point slides from the meeting of the 15th of October between the WP4 leader (FRCT) and the Regional Coordinators (Table 1), open to the participation of the SC members. This power point presents the regional proposals sent by each WP4 Regional Coordinator, as the result of a previews consultation of the respective OR's FW partners, with proposal of synergies implementations, at a multi-regional level. These proposals can be implemented through the identification of common goals in capacity building activities between FW-partners, in which are identified a common gain by the participant FW-partners. This process is an ongoing process.

The WP4 leader, in coordination with their Regional coordinators, will keep a close communications in order to report and interact with the WP7 leader (monitoring and evaluation) and the WP8 leader for dissemination of the capacity actions, namely in the FORWARD website and in FORWARD digital networks, as with other WP's of direct interest.

Implemented actions

- Presentation of the WP4 roadmap during the Kick off meeting to the GA partners, February 2019 in Las Palmas, Canary Islands;
- Presentation of a draft proposal to partners on WP4 during a GA meeting online – on the 19th of June 2019- 10h30 Azores time/ 12h30 Brussels time;
- A Workshop session with FORWARD SC partners on WP4 Capacity Plan (M7) during the meeting in Reunion Island – France;
- A regional meetings with the FW partners and eventual R&I key partners, identified in the WP2;
- A Regional Coordinator was appointed in representation of the WP4 in their respective OR's in the 14th of May 2020;
- Presentation of the WP4 progress and roadmap in the WP3 Subcoordinators kick off (17th of September);
- Meeting with the Regional Coordinators to present possible opportunities of synergies in capacity and training activities between regional partners in the FW project (15th October 2020) and analyze the development of the D4.2 report.

Planned short/medium term actions

- Implementation of referred capacitation activities by FW partners in their OR's, based on the activities foreseen in Annex 3 from D4.1;
- Feedback from the Regional Coordinators regarding the synergies to be implemented (requested in the 15th October 2020 meeting by the WP4 leader) – as a result of the regional meetings;
- Punctual meetings, as well one on one meetings(when required) with the Regional Coordinators for WP4;
- Close contact with the subordinators of the WP3 Thematic Working Groups in order to follow up their engagement in the capacitation actions;
- Continuous communication with WP2, WP5, WP6, WP7 and WP8 leaders, in further synergies and promotion of common goals in the FW project.
- Present the WP4 evolution to the Advisory Members in the FORWARD online meeting of the 22th October – challenge them to volunteer to lead capacity talks to the FW partners;
- Receive inputs from the WP4 RC regarding the results of the implementation of multi-regional synergies (regional meetings between the 26th and 30th of October)

CONCLUSIONS

The deliverable 4.2 plays a major role in the WP4 work package as it works as the common ground from which the singularities will be integrated, in an inclusive, synergetic process towards excellence, that can be analyzed also as a common FORWARD plan for the R&I actors in the OR's.

The D4.2 as a Common training programme for OR's R&I actors is a way to ensure that all the FW partners are engaged in a common process of capacitation, adjusted to their present state of maturity of participation in the Framework Programs. It's essential to have in to mind that to reach excellence we need to focus on inclusiveness, taking in to account that each OR are at a different stage in their maturity, experience and knowledge capacities, network outreach, level of participation in FP and human resources availability. Therefore, the adjustment should be a natural process to align the 9 Regional Capacity Plan with a common view focused in the final goal of FORWARD project. This may allow the FW partners to be open to possibilities of collaboration and synergies that starts with the FW project and may have influence beyond the project to the OR's R&I ecosystem, with concrete joint participation in Framework Programs projects.

The goal is to use synergies, at several levels (inter-regional partners; multi-regional partners; etc), to reinforce the R&I capabilities by empowering the ORs R&I actors with the adequate capacities to support and achieve their effective participation in European R&I Framework Programmes (H2020, FP9 and others).

The WP2 gave the science-based facts that were used by the WP4 leader and each OR to construct and implement their FORWARD Capacity Plan. The improvement of the cooperation and co-design and promotion of synergies will assure conditions for the OR's to develop skills and capacities of the actors and their R&I communities.

As an ultimate result the capacitation actions wants to have an impact in the current and future performance of the OR's R&I ecosystem in FP programs, reinforcing mutual knowledge and a strong link between the OR' R&I organizations. The graphic 1 illustrates the FORWARD common capacity plan for R&I ecosystem on WP4 and shows the strong commitment from all partners on investing in their R&I actors capacities. This points to a future of more active participation

by the OR's in the Framework Programmes and other EU funding opportunities for R&I and it represents also a starting point/development of stronger link between the OR's R&I actors, led by the FW partners.

Concluding in a positive note, the D4.2 is built to raise excellence in the OR's R&I ecosystem by transforming and adjusting the capacities of the OR's R&I ecosystem promoting collaboration within OR's and between OR's and beyond, as essential to keep the R&I communities in the OR's connected. Also it allows the OR's to prepare for present and future needs and challenges of their R&I actors, namely in the context of the Green Deal and the Horizonte Europe. The 9 Capacity Plans goes beyond the geographic limits, with innovative, synergetic and adjusted strategies of capacitation for the quadruple helix of the OR's R&I. This Plans are translated in to a common Capacity Plan that has in common the goal of improving performance, showcase and promote OR's excellence and ultimately increase the number of FP projects participation in the OR's R&I ecosystem.

REFERENCES

- I. *Horizon 2020 interim evaluation: maximizing the impact of EU research and innovation*, EC COM(2018) 2 final, <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/1/2018/EN/COM-2018-2-F1-EN-MAIN-PART-1.PDF>
- II. *The Knowledge Future: Intelligent policy choices for Europe 2050; Foresight on Key Long-term Transformations of European systems: Research, Innovation and Higher Education*, Madelin Report (KT2050), 2015] - https://ec.europa.eu/research/foresight/pdf/knowledge_future_2050.pdf
- III. *Grant Agreement number: 824550, FORWARD Project — H2020-SwafS-2018-2020/H2020-SwafS-2018-1*
- IV. *FORWARD Regional diagnoses built under the WP2* (Reunion Island with contributions from all FW partners)
- V. *Horizon 2020 interim evaluation: maximizing the impact of EU research and innovation*, EC COM(2018) 2 final, <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/1/2018/EN/COM-2018-2-F1-EN-MAIN-PART-1.PDF>
- VI. *Mutual Learning Event Report*, FORWARD project (NEXA), 2019
- VII. *Common technical position of the OR S3 Network regarding Component 5 – Interregional innovation investments*, March 31st of 2017, the Presidents of the Outermost Regions (ORs)
- VIII. *Work Package 4 - D4.1 Capacity building plan Report*, FORWARD Project (FRCT), July 2020

WP4 Regional coordinators

REGION	Regional Coordinator name	Email
Guadelupe	Sophie Larrieu	slarrieu@cr-guadeloupe.fr
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 624550.

Deliverables on WP4

Deliverable Number	Deliverable title	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D4.1	Capacity building plan	Report	Public	M18-M19*
D4.2	Common training programme for OR's R&I actors	Report	Public	M18-M22*
D4.3	Common training programme for OR's R&I officers	Report	Public	M25
D4.4	OR R&I Offices Operational and Sustainability Strategic for implementation	Report	Public	M36

*Suffered delay due to COVID context

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 624550.

Deliverable 4.2 - Common training programme for OR's R&I actors

Calendar

- ✓ **15th of October (Thursday):** deadline to reunite all info to include in D.42 report
- ✓ **From 20th to 22th of October (Tuesday-Thursday):** Make it available for inputs/comments in the FW google drive;
- ✓ **23th of October (Friday):** Integrate the inputs and comments on the final document;
- ✓ **From 26th -27th of October (Monday and Tuesday):** Make it available for voting remotely (if you agree this may be the best process) by doodle for the Steering Committee members;
- ✓ **28th October (Wednesday):** the Coordinator (Consulta Europa) submits in the platform the D4.2 Report to the EC

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 621436.

Note: deadline for submission is the 31th of October

REQUIRED INFORMATION FROM THE WP4 REGIONAL COORDINATORS

Regional CB Proposal list

Regional proposals to create multiregional synergies for capacity actions

REGIONS	Annex 3	Info on Synergies
Guadalupe		
Martinique		
Madeira		
Reunion		
Mayotte		
French Guiana		
Azores		
Saint Martin		
Canary Islands		

Feeds mutually

These synergies and the analyses of the CB actions will feed a common analysis to be included in the D4.2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 621436.

WP4 Regional coordinators proposals for multiregional synergies

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019740.

Canary Islands

- Initially, the idea is to train FW-CA partners and their ecosystem (research community, EU project managers, FW-CA-SUBCOORDINATORS, enterprises), so the idea is to offer them in Spanish;
- Each FW-CA partner will decide the training based on their needs and the public/target they want to reach;

We are open to different options.

We are now deciding on the type and conditions of the consultant we want to subcontract.

If other OR partners interested it's offered options in terms of availability (nº max of participants per course) and costs sharing.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019740.

PROPOSAL OPTIONS

Canary Islands

Plan A: participation on open online trainings offered by consultants where: Each partner decide who and how many people they want to enrol, attending to their budget and needs. For example: EURADIA: [Curso on line Elaboración de Proyectos de I+D+i de H2020 a HEurope](#). Each inscription costs 450 €/person.

Plan B: the consultant prepare and organise an online course ad-hoc for FW-CA partners where we can decide the contents based on our interest and needs.

EURADIA offer this course for aprox. 5.000 €, 16h (8 days, 2h/day); participants available max. 25-26. So, in that case, we should know how many FW-CA partners are interested in order to decide how many people per entity could participate. The idea is that the costs could be shared between FW-CA partners.

Plan A + Plan B: based on the partner needs and budget.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

Madeira

- Madeira has confirmed the possibility of synergies in line with what is already contracted with SaturnTech (EU projects proposal training and/or Innovation Management and/or Proposals writing and/or Proposals checking) and StartUp Madeira (Entrepreneurship for Researchers).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

PROPOSAL OPTIONS

Madeira

Option A: SaturnTech (<http://www.h2020proposals.eu/>), a consulting/training firm based in Spain. Ana Caires is the CEO of SaturnTechn and a native of Madeira. Works in Portuguese, Spanish and English, usually on a face-to-face regime, but which can be adapted to online

Option B: StartUp Madeira (<https://startupmadeira.eu/>), whose CEO is Carlos Soares Lopes, streamlines projects / actions of entrepreneurship and innovation in various aspects. Actions aimed at researchers should include the participation of invited external partners, including foreigners. It can be lectured in Portuguese and/or English.

For any financial detail regarding the implementation of this synergies it should be dealt with the WP4 Regional Coordinator from Madeira

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

Azores

- Azores FW partners - **University of the Azores; Regional Fund for Science and Technology** have confirmed their interest creating synergies for capacity building activities, namely in fellowships or/and trainings;
- The idea is to train FW-AZ partners in Portuguese, however the AZ FW partners are open to change it to English in case of forming synergies with other non Portuguese speaking regions;
- The Azorean FW partner **Chamber of Industry and Commerce from the Azores** is not interested in synergies, as it going to focus on SME's and micro companies and are opting for Portuguese trainings.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

PROPOSAL OPTIONS

Azores

- The type and conditions of the consultant/trainer we want to subcontract is still ongoing analysis, however these examples of capacity actions that could implement synergies:

FW partner	Type of Capacity action	Capacity action name	Skills to attain
FRCT	Training	Green Deal Challenges	Call on specific areas; Share of expertise in framework programs; SDG in Framework Programs
	Training	Capacitation in network - Networking to excellence	Exchange on good practice in networking and exchange examples of success; gain new insight regarding European consortium building.
	Advanced Training Skills - Fellowships	Brussels Training in the EU	For support services actors - network; consortium building; thematic approach; international outreach

For any financial detail regarding the implementation of this synergies it should be dealt with the

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

WP4 Regional Coordinator from Azores

forward

Martinique

- The FW-MAR partners are open to create synergies, in French;
- For more information all FW-partners interested should contact Philippe HUNEL, as the WP4 Regional Coordinator

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

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Mayotte

- Mayotte have confirmed their interest creating synergies for capacity building activities, namely in fellowships or/and trainings;
- The option of English is open in some of actions in the CBP.

Any other question related to the implementation process, namely financially details should be managed directly with the organizations involved.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101019710.

PROPOSAL OPTIONS

Mayote

Name/title of the Trainings	Goal & Skills	Target public	Proposal
Atelier sur la co-création et mise en œuvre de projets de recherche	Increase the participation in FP; e.g. writing successful R&I proposals; how to find EU opportunities;	R&I actors (both public & private)	In Mayotte with possibility to do have online session. Training in English if there is a possibility of synergies with another partner otherwise it will be in French
Comment intégrer les réseaux européens de recherche	Capacity building for networking and connectivity with EU clusters	Researchers	Online English session with collaboration building between researchers from Mayotte, other ORs and EU clusters. Need for synergy with other partners. Open for 2 researchers exchanges: short term mobility
Innovation et coopération entre les acteurs de R&D	Further analysis of the ability for business innovation opportunities and to contribute for the definition strategies to incorporate R&D for an ongoing/active business innovative processes and corporate policy. EU approach on funding for companies and European programs, opportunities and challenges for regional companies.	R&I actors (both public & private)	Online session in English if there is a possibility of synergies with another partner.

Any financial detail for this synergies implementation should be dealt with the WP4 Regional Coordinator for Mayote

French Guyane

- FG FW-partners are interested in implementing multiregional synergies: CTG; UG; GDI.
- These trainings can be lectured in English or in French – to be agreed between the partners;
- The proposal is to share the value of the training and implement it online (videoconference).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

PROPOSAL OPTIONS

French Guyane

These are only examples. Find more informations on the Annex 3 for all the actions proposed for multiregional synergies

FORWARD partner	Type of capacity action	Name/title of the Capacity action	Goal & Skills training	Target public	Total budgeted foreseen
CTG	Training	Training on opportunities H2020	Give Information dedicated to H2020 and funding opportunities for French Guiana candidates to foster their participation in HORIZON funding programs	Potential stakeholders or candidates for H2020 financing	2 500,00 €
UG	Fellowships to attend training abroad	Project management and financial reporting of European Projects	Give skills for planning, budgeting, accounting, financial reporting, internal control, auditing of the project with the aim of managing project resources properly and achieving the project's objectives	Potential candidates for H2020 financing and Participants from support services	1 500,00 €
GDI	Training	Training on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	Identify opportunities, develop business plans and capture the value created, Learn to collaborate effectively with other actors and specialists internal and external to your company or in specific ecosystems, How to grow your customer base through inbound and outbound marketing	Researchers and business owners	2 500,00 €

Reunion Island

- The FW-REUN partners are open to create synergies in the implementation of some actions, as well as combining these WP4 actions with other WP's;
- These collaborative actions should be in English in their opinion.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101015000

PROPOSAL OPTIONS

Reunion Island

Plan A: Organize in Brussels a common training multiregional and multi-WP, during 2021, in 2 specific thematic areas (HSS and ENERGY), in order to:

- **implement WP4 with trainings (on EU Policies and networking skills) and fellowships to attend training abroad**
- implement WP3 with thematic actions
- implement WP5 with networking between OR and other stk in BXL (to be identified)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101015000

PROPOSAL OPTIONS

Reunion Island

Plan B: develop bilateral cooperation's with some regions and organize webinars on " Demystifying European programmes for participants that do not know or know very little about the framework programme ».

For more details on this proposal the interested regions should contact the WP4 Regional Coordinator from Reunion Island

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019100.

Guadalupe

- The FW-REUN partners are open to create synergies, in French in some cases and in French or in English in other cases;
- For more information all FW-partners interested should contact Sophie, as the WP4 Regional Coordinator

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019100.

PROPOSAL OPTIONS

Guadelupe

These are only examples. Find more informations on the Annex 3 for all the actions proposed for multiregional synergies

FORWARD partner	Name/title of the Capacity action	Goal & Skills training	Target public	Total budgeted forseen	Observations
REG GUA	Training Montage and writing of proposals	Increase the competitiveness of proposals focusing on the Excellence, impact and Implementation sections	Public and private researchers	2 500 €	Interested for synergies, in French , ok for sharing the value of the training, by videoconference
REG GUA	Training Development of european networks for energy domain	Increase the capacity to detect and connect to the networks and people active in H2020 (RUP and European partners)	Public and private researchers	2 500 €	Interested for synergies, in English or in French , ok for sharing the value of the training, by videoconference
UA	Training in Montage and writing of proposals	Increase the competitiveness of proposals focusing on the Excellence, impact and Implementation sections	R&D organizations and actor and researchers	2 500 €	Interested for synergies, in French , ok for sharing the value of the training, by videoconference
UA	English Training	Increase the capacity to detect and connect to the networks and people active in H2020 (RUP and European partners)	R&D organizations and actor and researchers	2 500 €	Interested for synergies, in English or in French , ok for sharing the value of the training, by videoconference

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

forward

Martinique

- The FW-MAR partners are open to create synergies, in French and English – to be agreed between FW partners;
- For more information all FW-partners interested should contact Philippe Hunel, as WP4 Regional Coordinator.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

forward

PROPOSAL OPTIONS

Martinique

These are only examples. Find more informations on the Annex 3 for all the actions proposed for multiregional synergies

Name/title of the Capacity action	Goal & Skills training	Target public	Total budgeted foreseen	Observations
Training Montage of proposals	Design a project that meets the requirements of the European Commission, understand the rules and procedures for participating in H2020 and Horizon Europe. Deepening knowledge of the entire process from submission to dissemination of results, including financial rules	Public and private researchers, companies, public actors, R&D organizations, CTM services	833 €	Interested for synergies, Interested in collaborating through training webinars with a similar level of knowledge.
workshop on project writing	How to write a competitive proposal/Manage and monitor a successful project	researchers, actors R&D	833 €	Interested in collaborating in French
Collaborative projects in FP Programs Create networking links	1) How to create a consortium? 2) How to network SMEs-researchers? 3) Acquire new knowledge, working methods or strategies with more actors	Public and private researchers, companies, public actors, R&D organizations, CTM services	833 €	Interested for synergies, Interested in collaborating through training webinars with a similar level of knowledge.

Saint Martin

- At this time the partner did not express interest in synergies, however they are open to proposals;
- Due to the small ecosystem St. Martin have just 2 trainings foreseen in the context of the FW GA budgeted.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

Saint Martin

Foreseen trainings

FORWARD partner	Name/title of the Capacity action	Goal & Skills training	Target public
COMSM	Training on Introduction to EU FUNDING	Understanding the EU levers in funds	Stakeholders, general public
COMSM	Training on H2020 an opportunity of innovation growth	RIS 3 innovation policies for 21-27	Stakeholders, public officers, policy makers

CCISM has no budget for WP4 activities

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 624155

Analysis of the Annex 3 proposals

Transform in to a **graphic** that represents the **common FORWARD Capacity Building Plan for D4.2**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 624155

Common areas of definition for the capacity building activities

These are the areas (still ongoing work) in which the regional CB proposals will be defined and divided in order to reach a common representation of the OR's CBP in FW into a graphic - to be included in the D4.2

FORWARD - Target areas for capacity building		
FW skills	EU Funding	HR capacities
Management in Innovation	H2020 / HEurope	Financial management
Project Manager	LIFE + and BEST	Training in specific areas – based on the WP3 areas
Identification of calls, successful proposals and managing funds	European funds regionally managed (FSE, FEDER, INTERREG B, etc.)	Development of soft skills (network building; team management; time; managing)
Communicating science	Call for Tenders - UE	Coaching in science
Stakeholders engagement strategy	Others EU funds managed by the EC (Maritime funds, INTERREG EUROPE, MAES, etc.)	Entrepreneurship
Knowledge transfer	Deep knowledge and alignment on EU networks, like ERA, RIS3 and Regional development	Writing impact sections

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

FORWARD - Delivreable D4.2

FORWARD Common Capacity Plan for OR's R&I actors

■ FORWARD Skills ■ EU Funding ■ Human Resources ■ To be defined

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

Next steps:

- Contact your FW regional partners and present these offers of multiregional synergies for CBP – with Annex 3 info and the following information on this power point (you should transform and adapt this pw);
- Come back to me with information regarding the implementation of these synergies, in order to update also the Annex 3 with this information and check the eligibility with the coordinator of any financial details;
- Revision of D4.2 report – all FW-partners will be called to give their input on this document: **from 20th to 22th of October (Tuesday-Thursday).**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 10101502.

For any further questions or support please contact the WP4 leader (FRCT)

Thank you

Lina Silveira
FRCT Project manager for FORWARD

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 10101502.

ANNEX 2: The graphical representation of the 9 OR's Capacity Plan proposals²

² Based on the analyses of the WP4 leader of the Annex 3 table from D4.1, delivered by each OR

CBP Martinique

- Entrepreneurship and innovation
- Project management skills
- Networking and collaborative actions
- Training on HORIZON EUROPE

CBP Reunion Island

- Awareness sessions on FP
- Training on MSCA proposals for researchers
- Training on RRI for researchers
- Training/Workshop on H2020 for researchers
- Training for HSS researchers
- Training on networking for researchers and entrepreneurs
- Workshop/Trainings on competitiveness for researchers and entrepreneurs
- Training in communication and network for researchers
- Workshop focus on specific calls for researchers
- Workshop on ERA, RIS3 and Regional development for R&I actors

CBP Mayote

- Training on Framework Projects
- Innovation and cooperation
- Training on networking and connectivity with EU clusters

CBP Guadalupe

- Training in thematic networks for researchers
- Project management and development in FP
- Fellowships on proposal co-creation and project implementation
- English Training for networking
- Technology transfer training

CBP St. Martin

- Training on project management and development focused on researchers
- Training on project managing for R&I actors